

A STUDY OF EFFECT OF AGE AND GENDER ON STRESS OF ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract

The aim of the present research was to investigate the effect of age and gender on stress among adolescents. The sample was consisted of 120 male and female subjects in the age range 11 to 18 years taken from schools of Meerut city. The subjects were divided into two groups according to their age early adolescents (12-14 years) and late adolescents (16-18 years). Each group was consisted of two groups of Male (60 Ss) & female (60 Ss) subjects. In this way a 2x2 factorial design was employed in the research. Data was collected with the help of standardized student stress scale. The obtained data were statistically analyzed by Mean, SD and ANOVA. The result indicated that age and gender was found to be significantly effective on stress among adolescents.

Key words: Age, Gender, Stress, mental health

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Introduction

It is said that “Health is like money; but we never have a true idea of its value until we lose it. It means that health of a man is everything to stay happy in his life. If a person is healthy psychologically as well as physiologically, he can enjoy all the moment. According to world health organization (1948) health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. Both and Roberts et al. (2012) revealed that people who are physically in active and does not exercise, they have found to be increasing vulnerability chronic disease. Ashakiran & deepthi, (2012) studied that junk and fast food are considering in tending to cholesterol problem, stroke and heart disease, BP issues and obesity etc. Smoking and tobacco are the major cause of increasing health disability on a large scale. West (2017) found that tobacco and smoking consumers reported that cigarettes deliver

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nicotine rapidly to the brain that is enjoyable for them. Similarly excessive use of drugs such as alcohol, medication and some chemical substances affect social life, school life, married life and physio-psychological health and performance too (Ricketts, 2016)

On the other hand poverty is identified as the highest threaten to health disorders and disability (Swinnerton, 2006). The environment factor can be included also in increasing health issues. It is identified that poor air quality water and sanitation are important in leading health problems (Correll, 2020). Adolescence is an important stage of human development identified as changes in neurological, Hormonal, psychological and social. During this stage adolescents have to cope up with several stressors such as physical, sexual especially changes in puberty stage, school life, relationships with friends and family members, working life and career choice etc. The consequences of stress in this period can be existed as depression and anxiety, suicidal ideation substances abuse and anti-social behavior (Krapic & Hudek-Knezevic et al., 2015). A study suggested that adolescence is one of the most important changing periods when anxiety and depression frequently occur (Hummon 2009). Stress is very common problem that is experienced by people positively and negatively when people have no resources to sort out the problem then stress occurs and if people cope up with the stress, then stress does not occur. It influences people mentally and physically both.

According to Hinkle (1973), Stress denoted as force, pressure and straining referring firstly to an individual or a person is organ or psychological powers. Salleh (2008) revealed that short-term stress gives strength to the immune system but long-term stress tends to weak immune system. Bhargav and Trivedi (2018) studied that people who are facing stressful life that makes them many physio-psychological disease emotional stability is an important factor among resilience, coping mechanisms etc. which decrease the vulnerability to mental and physical problems. People who have good emotional stability they have better life as compared to those who are emotionally weak. Weak emotional stability creates neurotic disorders. Some studies indicated that emotional stability is very important factor in leading cheerful life and better well-being. Scott (1968) stated that emotional stability is one of the seventh important factors which indicate better mental health. Smith and Segal (2011) said that people who are healthy emotionally coping up easily with the stressful situation.

Method

The main objective of the present research was to study the effect of age and gender on stress. The study was guided by a two-tailed hypothesis that will be a significant effect (and interaction effects) of age and gender on stress among adolescents.

Sample

The sample for study was 120 male and female adolescents' subjects in the age range 11 to 18 years old that was taken from schools of Meerut City. The subjects were divided into two groups according to their age early adolescents (12-14 Years) and late adolescents (16-18 years), each age group was again consisted of two groups of male and female subjects.

Tools

Following tools were used to gather data for the research:

1. Personal Information Schedule: It was used to get personal and demographic details of subjects required for sampling and discussion.
2. Students Stress Scale: It is developed by Dr. Alchitar (2011) The measure of stress comprises of 51 items (41 positives and 10 negative) on a five-point scale. The co-efficient alpha reliability and test-retest reliability were determined. It was 0.78 and 0.71 and construct validity was used of .72.

The Procedure of Data Collection

The data was collected individually after getting informed consent from the subjects.

Results

The obtained data were statistically analyzed by Mean, SD and ANOVA. The obtained results are shown in the following tables and their detailed interpretation and discussion is as follows.

Table 1 F-ratio, SD and Mean stress scores for the groups of age and gender.

Variable	Variability	Mean	SD	F-ratio
Gender	Male	195.20	13.80	49.72**
	Female	196.83	112.600	

Stress and Age

The study of table 1 indicated that obtained F-value showing a significant effect of gender on stress [F (1, 116=49.72' P<.01)]. Table-1 also showing that stress score of female adolescent subjects (M=196.83, SD=12.600) was significantly higher as compared to Male adolescent subjects (M=195.20, SD=12.60). This means that the two groups differ significantly and the

directional hypothesis that there will be a significant effect of gender on stress among adolescents is accepted.

Discussion

The result indicated that there was a significant effect of gender on stress among adolescents and it was found that female have shown higher score on stress. The reason can be behind the fact that these girls are more sensitive soft kind hearted, emotionally weak and less strong as compared to boys so they get stressed easily some studies indicated that female experience higher scores on interpersonal stress generation in urban in the comparison to urban boys (Starrs and Abela et al., 2017). Studies also have shown the gender differences on depression among adolescents and it is also revealed that female have shown higher scores on depression scale as compared to male (Costella et al., 2006) Singh and Upadhyay (2008) studied that female subjects are found to be more stressed as compared to boys. Vijay and Gonsalves et al. (2020) studied that it is also found that Indian girls are more stressful than boys (Verma & Gupta, 1990), because girls have reported differently towards the stress as compared to boys (Bouma,2010). Female reported higher scores on stress & and anxiety than boys (Singh & Pandey et al., (2021). It was also revealed that girls are reported high stress score to compare with boys (Starrs & Abela., 2017; Costella et al., 2006).

Conclusion

So, it can be concluded that gender was found to be significantly effective on stress. Further, it can be concluded that female is more stressful than males.

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